

A Phenyl Propanoid Glycoside from *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*

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We have earlier reported many new iridoids from the seeds and leaves of *Nyctanthes arbor-tristis*¹. Of these, Arbortristoside A and B were found to have anticancer activity² against methylcholanthrene induced fibrosarcoma in rats. The other iridoids reported from the seeds are nyctanthoside³, 6 β -hydroxyloganin and arbortristoside C, D and E⁴. Recently, we have isolated⁵ a phenylpropanoid glycoside, desrhamnosylverbascoside (calceolarioside A⁶) from the leaves of the plant. Further investigation of the minor fractions from the MeOH extract of the seeds resulted in the isolation of a new phenylpropanoid glycoside designated as nyctoside A (1).

Results and Discussion

Nyctoside A (1), C₂₈H₃₄O₁₅, an amorphous powder, and its ir and uv spectra (see Experimental) suggested the presence of a caffeoyl moiety. Acid hydrolysis of 1 afforded D-glucose and D-xylose, characterised by paper chromatography. Acetylation of 1 with NaOAc-Ac₂O yielded a nonaacetate (2). The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data of 1 and 2 (vide Experimental) (Tables 1 and 2) reveal all the structural features of the molecule. The ¹H nmr spectral data of 1 showed doublets at δ 6.16 and 7.46 for *trans*-olefinic protons (δ 116.7 and 147.7 for 1 and 117.7 and 144.6 ppm

for 2; α' - and β' -C) of caffeoyl moiety and a triplet at δ 5.06 assignable to the ester-bearing methine proton. These observations showed that the caffeoyl moiety was linked through C-4' hydroxyl of glucose (71.0 in 1 and 68.9 in 2; C-4') as in acetoside⁷.

TABLE 1-¹H Nmr DATA (δ) OF COMPOUNDS 1 AND 2 (300.13 MHz)

H	1	2*
2	6.58 (br s)	7.05 (br s)
5	6.55 (d, <i>J</i> 7.8 Hz)	7.10 (br s)
6	6.45 (dd, <i>J</i> 2, 7.8 Hz)	7.10 (br s)
α	3.08 (m)	3.68 (m)
β	2.66 (m)	2.88 (m)
1'	4.44 (d, <i>J</i> 7.5 Hz)	4.48 (d, <i>J</i> 8.8 Hz)
2'	3.44 (dd, <i>J</i> 7.8, 9.4 Hz)	3.68 (m)
3'	4.11 (t, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz)	5.26 (t, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz)
4'	5.06 (t, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz)	5.05 (t, <i>J</i> 9.5 Hz)
5'	3.71 (m)	3.68 (m)
6'	3.59(m)	4.12 (m)
	3.88 (dd, <i>J</i> 7.7, 10.7 Hz)	
1''	4.23 (d, <i>J</i> 7.6 Hz)	4.52 (d, <i>J</i> 7.0 Hz)
2''	3.34 (dd, <i>J</i> 7.8, 9.4 Hz)	4.99 (t, <i>J</i> 9.3 Hz)
3''	3.59 (m)	5.13 (t, <i>J</i> 8.3 Hz)
4''	3.71 (m)	4.90 (m)
5''	3.47 (m)	3.55 (dd, <i>J</i> 8.6, 11.9 Hz)
	3.88 (dd, <i>J</i> 7.7, 10.7 Hz)	3.88, (br d)
α'	6.16 (d, <i>J</i> 15.8 Hz)	6.3 (d, <i>J</i> 16 Hz)
β'	7.45 (d, <i>J</i> 15.8 Hz)	7.61 (d, <i>J</i> 16 Hz)
2'''	6.93 (d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz)	7.38 (d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz)
5'''	6.66 (d, <i>J</i> 7.7 Hz)	7.24 (d, <i>J</i> 8.4 Hz)
6'''	6.82 (dd, <i>J</i> 2, 7 Hz)	7.41 (dd, <i>J</i> 2, 8.6 Hz)

*Acetoxy protons from nine OAc groups at δ 1.93, 1.95, 1.98, 2.04, 2.04, 2.27, 2.29, 2.30 and 2.31 ppm.

The presence of a 3,4-dihydroxyphenyl ether moiety was apparent from the ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data (3.08, m and 3.68, m; 2H- α for 1 and 2; 2.66, m and 2.88, m; 2H- β for 1 and 2; 72.1 and 69.8; α -C for 1 and 2; 36.4 and 35.3; β -C for 1 and 2). This was confirmed from the FAB mass spectrum of 2 by the appearance of a peak at m/z 751 (species a) generated from the molecular ion peak (M⁺ 988) by the loss of 3,4-diacetoxycinnamoyl ethyl ether moiety (237 m.u.). The conclusion that the ether moiety is linked

through C-1' of glucose was derived from a comparison of the anomeric proton signal (δ 4.44) of glucose in **1** with that (δ 4.37, 1H, d, J 7.5 Hz) in conandroside⁸. The anomeric proton signal of xylose, however, appeared at δ 4.23. The above values of the anomeric protons of glucose and xylose in **1** (104.2, C-1'; 105.1, C-1'') as also those (4.48, 1'-H and 4.52, 1''-H) in **2** (100.7, C-1'; 100.5, C-1'') clearly show that both the sugars are linked in the β -form.

That xylose and not glucose was the terminal sugar, was confirmed from the FAB mass spectrum of the nonacetate (**2**) by the appearance of a base peak at m/z 259 corresponding to xylose triacetate residue (b). Occurrence of other peaks at m/z 493 (c) and 535 (d) also confirmed xylose to be the terminal sugar as the ion species (c and d) lacked xylose triacetate residue which was lost easily during their formation. The formation of the fragment ion at m/z 493 could be explained by the loss of xylose

triacetate residue from the ion fragment at m/z 751 followed by the uptake of one hydrogen radical while the simultaneous loss of xylose triacetate moiety and diacetoxybenzene from the peak at m/z 988 followed by rearrangement leads to the ion species at m/z 535.

In the ¹H nmr spectrum of nyctoside A, there appeared a double-doublet corresponding to one proton at δ 3.34. The chemical shift and coupling constant of this proton was typical of 2'-H of glucose (3.38, 1H, dd, J 7.8, 9.5 Hz) in orbanchoside⁹, wherein a rhamnose unit was linked to 2'-hydroxyl of glucose. This clearly indicates that the xylose in nyctoside A is attached to glucose through its 2'-hydroxyl group. The structure of the phenylpropanoid was further confirmed from the detailed ¹³C nmr spectral data of **1** and its nonacetate **2** (Table 2). Thus nyctoside A stands as 1'-O- β -D-(3,4-dihydroxy- β -phenyl ethyl)-4'-O-caffeoyl- β -D-xylopyranosyl(1'' \rightarrow 2')glucopyranoside (1).

Nyctoside A is therefore an isomer of conandroside isolated from *Conandron ramoidioides*⁸ in which the xylose linkage was assigned to position-3'. The occurrence of phenylpropanoid glycoside in *N. arbor-tristis* is in conformity with the earlier observation of the co-existence of phenylpropanoid glycosides with iridoid glucosides in plants belonging to the families Schrophulariaceae, Bignoniaceae, Labiatae, Oleaceae, Pedaliaceae and Verbenaceae¹⁰.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. ¹H nmr (300.13 MHz) and ¹³C nmr (75.46 MHz) spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM 300 L supercon spectrometer in CD₃OD and CDCl₃ for **1** and **2** respectively, at the Centre of Advanced Studies Facility of the Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta. Chemical shifts are presented in values relative to TMS. Silica gel (Acme's) 100-200 mesh was used for cc. The separation was monitored by tlc (silica gel G).

Isolation of nyctoside A: Coarsely powdered seeds (2 kg) were defatted and then extracted with MeOH at room temperature. The MeOH extract was dried and subjected to cc over silica gel. CHCl₃ : MeOH : H₂O (80 : 20 : 1) eluates yielded a gum which was rechromatographed over silica gel. Elution with CHCl₃-MeOH-H₂O (65 : 25 : 1) afforded **1** as an amorphous hygroscopic powder (500 mg), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350 (OH), 1 705 (α,β -unsatd. ester), 1 632 (C=C), 1 600 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 218, 240(sh), 288, 329 nm; ¹H nmr data in Table 1; ¹³C nmr data in Table 2.

Acetylation of nyctoside A (1). Compound **1** (150 mg) was refluxed with Ac₂O (3 ml) and fresh NaOAc in an oil-bath for 4 h. Workup in the usual way afforded the nonacetate (**2**; 120 mg), m.p. 75-77°, m/z 988 (M⁺) C₄₆H₅₂O₂₄, 751, 535, 493, 259 (base peak); ¹H nmr data in Table 1 and ¹³C nmr data in Table 2.

TABLE 2-¹³C Nmr DATA (δ) OF COMPOUNDS **1** AND **2** (75.5 MHz)

C	1	2*
1	131.7	137.5
2	117.2	123.0
3	145.9	140.6
4	144.5	141.9
5	115.5	123.8
6	121.4	127.1
α	72.1	69.8
β	36.4	35.3
1'	104.2	100.7
2'	77.4	73.5
3'	74.7	70.6
4'	71.0	68.9
5'	75.2	71.3
6'	66.7	62.0
1''	105.1	100.5
2''	72.5	71.3
3''	75.8	72.7
4''	74.8	69.3
5''	69.4	67.7
α'	116.7	117.7
β'	147.7	144.6
1'''	127.8	132.7
2'''	116.9	124.0
3'''	146.6	142.6
4'''	149.5	143.9
5'''	114.6	123.1
6'''	123.1	126.6
CO	168.6	165.0

*Additional carbon signals from acetoxy groups at δ 170.1, 169.9, 169.7, 169.3 (2 \times CO), 168.1 (2 \times CO), 167.9, 167.7 and 20.5 ppm (9 \times Me).

Hydrolysis of nyctoside A (1) : Compound 1 (120 mg) was treated with 1N H₂SO₄ (35 ml) at 100° for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then neutralised with BaCO₃, the insoluble material was removed by filtration and the solution extracted with EtOAc. The aqueous solution was evaporated under reduced pressure and the sugars were identified as D-glucose and D-xylose by pc.

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